

Correction

Correction: Tsakalidis et al. Design and Implementation of a Versatile OpenHAB IoT Testbed with a Variety of Wireless Interfaces and Sensors. *Telecom* 2023, 4, 597–610

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Reference Correction

There was an error in the original publication [1]. The 32nd reference was inaccurately stated as “SYNERGIES—Coordinating Energy-Efficiency and Demand Response Actions in the Building Sector”.

A correction has been made to the References section, the corrected 32nd reference appears below:

“Shaping consumer-inclusive data pathwaYs towards the eNERGY transition, through a reference Energy data Space implementation. Available online: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069839> (accessed on 13 March 2023).”

The authors state that the scientific conclusions are unaffected. This correction was approved by the Academic Editor. The original publication has also been updated.

Reference

1. Tsakalidis, S.; Tsoulos, G.; Kontaxis, D.; Athanasiadou, G. Design and Implementation of a Versatile OpenHAB IoT Testbed with a Variety of Wireless Interfaces and Sensors. *Telecom* 2023, 4, 597–610. [[CrossRef](#)]

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